

This readme file is mainly to describe each file in " Experimental data about Talc".

File 1: Experimental data about Talc.xlsx

This spreadsheet presents the experimental data obtained. The wave signal filename in the last column of the spreadsheet, which corresponds to the pressure, is in the archive "File 3. wave signal.zip".

File 2: Four-order Eulerian finite strain fitting.xlsx

This spreadsheet was used for fitting the experimental data to obtain the elastic moduli. The Solver Function of Excel is used in it.

File 3: wave signal.zip

This archive contains the original wave signals acquired during the experiment.